

Factors influencing adjusted risk for pre-eclampsia: a Bulgarian cross-sectional study*

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Received 25 July 2025 ♦ Accepted 8 April 2026 ♦ Published 15 June 2026

Citation: Angelova A, Zlateva S, Dimcheva P, Stoilov P, Mihova A, Mihaylov R, Pencheva B, Velikova T (2026) Factors influencing adjusted risk for pre-eclampsia: a Bulgarian cross-sectional study. *Pharmacia* 73: e166725. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e166725>

Abstract

Pre-eclampsia (PE) is a complex multisystem disorder posing significant risks to both maternal and fetal health; therefore, accurate prediction is crucial for early intervention and improving outcomes for both the mother and fetus.

Material and methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted of 381 pregnant women with available medical history data (mean age of 30 years, range 18–43), all carrying singleton pregnancies. Maternal serum levels of free beta human chorionic gonadotropin (FBHCG), pregnancy-associated plasma protein-A (PAPP-A) and placental growth factor (PIGF) were measured using the B-R-A-H-M-S Fast Screen pre I plus 3.1 system on the KRYPTOR platform (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Risk assessment for PE was performed using an integrated software algorithm that incorporated biochemical markers and maternal clinical characteristics.

Results: The study population included 24.1% active smokers, 36.7% of women with a body mass index (BMI) > 25, 1.6% with a history of arterial hypertension (AH) and 10 patients with diabetes. A total of 22 (5.8%) of 291 women with available data reported a maternal history of PE. The mean levels of FBHCG, PAPP-A and PIGF were 43.28 ± 1.51 IU/mL, 5.39 ± 0.17 IU/mL and 47.93 ± 1.61 pg/mL, respectively. Risk assessment identified eight women (2.1%) at increased risk for PE at 34 weeks (adjusted risk [AR] < 1:70), 35 (9.2%) at 37 weeks (AR < 1:70) and 21 (5.5%) at 40 weeks (AR < 1:15). Normal BMI was associated with a significantly lower risk for PE compared to elevated BMI across all gestational time points ($p < 0.001$). Previous AH was associated with increased risk, reaching statistical significance at 40 weeks (AR 1:7, $p < 0.001$). Patients with diabetes showed a trend toward a higher risk of PE; however, this result did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: AR for PE correlated with the biochemical parameters and BMI, diabetes and AH. Measurement and further evaluation of these parameters are crucial for normal development and a positive pregnancy outcome. However, they should always be interpreted in the context of the mother's clinical findings and overall health.

Keywords

Adjusted risk, arterial hypertension, diabetes, free beta human chorionic gonadotropin, FBHCG, placental growth factor, PIGF, pregnancy-associated plasma protein-A, PAPP-A, pre-eclampsia, prenatal screening, risk assessment

* This article is part of: "Bridging Science and Innovation: Advances in Diagnosis, Therapy, and Translational Medicine: Insights from the Second SUMMIT Conference", edited by Georgi Momekov, Ivan Padjen, Naim Mahroum.

Introduction

Pre-eclampsia (PE) complicates 2%–8% of pregnancies and occurs most commonly during the second half of pregnancy. While overall rates of PE remain static, rates of severe PE appear to have increased over recent decades. Moreover, PE is associated with more than 50,000 maternal deaths and over 500,000 fetal deaths globally (Karrar et al. 2024). PE is a global health problem because it causes lifelong economic and personal suffering and burden. Its multifactorial pathogenesis, which essentially causes placental, vascular, renal, and immunological dysfunction, results in increased susceptibility to hypertension and chronic kidney disease. With treatment being limited and along with significant morbidity, it poses a risk to both the mother and fetus (Turbeville and Sasser 2020).

The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidelines (National Guideline Alliance 2019) classify a woman as high risk for PE if there is a history of hypertensive disease during a previous pregnancy or maternal disease, including chronic kidney disease, autoimmune disease, diabetes, or chronic hypertension. Women are at moderate risk if they are nulliparous; ≥ 40 years of age; have a body mass index (BMI) ≥ 35 kg/m²; a family history of PE; a multifetal pregnancy; or a pregnancy interval of more than 10 years (Fox et al. 2019). To identify pregnant women at risk of PE, several biomarkers have been developed. First-trimester screening for aneuploidies relies on biomarkers such as pregnancy-associated plasma protein-A (PAPP-A) and free beta human chorionic gonadotropin (FBHCG), which are tested before 11 weeks (Rode et al. 2025), and some of these could also be useful for PE screening. The Fetal Medicine Foundation (FMF) established a screening protocol for PE using parameters such as mean arterial pressure (MAP), uterine artery pulsatility index (UtA-PI), and biomarkers such as placental growth factor (PIGF), with the option to include PAPP-A (Akolekar et al. 2013). It is important to test for these markers collected between 11 and 14 weeks of pregnancy. This screening model could identify approximately 75% of preterm delivery cases before 37 weeks, with a screen-positive rate of 10% (Wright et al. 2015; O’Gorman et al. 2016).

The aim was to evaluate markers for PE risk assessment, including FBHCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF. FBHCG is a hormone mostly associated with maintaining early pregnancy by supporting the endometrium and exerting vital immunomodulatory and hormonal effects. Since PAPP-A is a protein crucial for fetal development because it is needed for implantation of the fetus and overall placental health, and PIGF is a protein produced by the placenta that is responsible for the vascular development of the placenta, with levels different for every gestational week, these biomarkers combined with maternal characteristics can provide a much better picture of placental and fetal health than ultrasound examinations by themselves. Furthermore, lower levels of PAPP-A and FBHCG are associated with pregnancy complications such as trisomies, stillbirth, low birth weight, and PE. Low PIGF is also associated with poor outcomes and is

generally low in PE patients, indicating low placental perfusion. Therefore, every factor should be further investigated and interpreted in the context of gestational age.

Methods

Subjects

A total of 381 pregnant women with relevant medical history data were analyzed: mean age 30 years (18–43), all with one fetus. Data were collected retrospectively over 1 year from pregnant women undergoing routine first-trimester screening.

All women completed a questionnaire about additional medical information. After completing the questionnaire, they agreed to the data collection and analysis. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Parameters and analyzers

Maternal serum was tested for FBHCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF using the B-R-A-H-M-S Fast Screen pre I plus 3.1 and KRYPTOR (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The latter is an analyzer that uses a measuring principle called time-resolved amplified cryptate emission (TRACE). TRACE is based on research for which the French chemist Jean-Marie Lehn received a Nobel Prize in Chemistry in 1987. Implementing this technology with specialized software makes it possible to establish different panels for risk assessment in the first and second trimesters of pregnancy. First-trimester PE screening combines maternal characteristics, obstetric history, biophysical markers, and maternal serum biomarkers. There is also the possibility of detecting first-trimester trisomies 13, 18, and 21. The second trimester can provide risk calculations for trisomies 13, 18, and 21 and neural tube defect (NTD).

Risk assessment for PE was performed using the integrated, proprietary software provided with the KRYPTOR system. The software is commercially available as part of the analyzer package and applies validated algorithms for first-trimester screening. Input variables include maternal characteristics (e.g., age, BMI), obstetric history (e.g., previous hypertension), and biochemical markers (FBHCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF). The output consists of individualized adjusted risk (AR) estimates for PE at different gestational time points (34, 37, and 40 weeks), expressed as risk ratios.

The analyzed variables in this study included maternal demographic and clinical characteristics (age, BMI, smoking status, history of arterial hypertension, diabetes, and family history of PE), as well as serum biomarker levels. The primary outcome was the calculated AR for PE at specified gestational ages.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was primarily performed using the integrated software of the B-R-A-H-M-S KRYPTOR platform (Thermo Fisher Scientific), which applies validated algo-

Figure 1. Mean levels of FBhCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF in the tested subjects.

Figure 2. Adjusted risk (AR) for PE at weeks 34, 37, and 40.

rithms for risk calculation based on maternal characteristics, obstetric history, and biochemical markers (FBhCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF). The software generates individual risk estimates for adverse pregnancy outcomes, including PE and chromosomal abnormalities, using predefined statistical models.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the study population. Continuous variables are presented as mean (range), while categorical variables are presented as frequencies and percentages. Where applicable, comparisons between groups were performed using standard statistical methods, e.g., Student's *t*-test or chi-square test. A *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographics

Women included in the study had a mean age of 30 years, with a range of 18–43. Information was also collected according to smoking status, how many women had a body mass index (BMI) > 25, how many had previous AH, and whether they were diagnosed with diabetes. Only 22 of 291 patients (5.8%) reported having a mother with documented PE. Active smokers were 92 (24.1%), 140 (36.7%) women had a BMI > 25, six (1.6%) had previous AH, and 10 (2.6%) had diabetes (five with gestational diabetes,

three with type 1 diabetes, and two with type 2 diabetes). One patient (0.3%) had systemic lupus, and two patients (0.5%) presented with antiphospholipid syndrome.

Levels of FBhCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF

The mean levels of FBhCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF were 43.28 ± 1.51 IU/mL, 5.39 ± 0.17 IU/mL, and 47.93 ± 1.61 pg/mL, respectively (Fig. 1).

Adjusted risk of PE

A software algorithm for prenatal screening identified eight women (2.1%) with AR for PE at week 34 (AR < 1:70), 35 (9.2%) at week 37 (AR < 1:70), and 21 (5.5%) at week 40 (AR < 1:15) (Fig. 2).

Normal BMI was associated with a lower risk for PE compared to obesity ($p < 0.001$) at week 34 (AR 1:39,950 vs. 1:11,539, respectively), week 37 (AR 1:2468 vs. 1:967, respectively), and week 40 (AR 1:276 vs. 1:136, respectively). A higher risk of PE was found in patients with diabetes ($p > 0.05$) and a history of AH, significant at week 40 (AR 1:7, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 3).

Higher levels of FBhCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF were also observed in patients with normal BMIs (Fig. 4).

Additional analyses revealed a higher risk for PE in patients with diabetes, without reaching significance ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 5).

Figure 3. Comparison between BMI and PE risk at week 34 (A), week 37 (B), and week 40 (C).

Figure 4. Comparison between BMI and levels of FBHCG (A), PAPP-A (B), and PIGF (C).

Figure 5. Diabetes and PE risk at different gestational weeks.

A higher risk of PE was also found in patients with previous AH, significant at week 40 (AR 1:7, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 6), and a higher risk was established at weeks 34 and 37, without reaching significance (Fig. 7).

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the usefulness of three maternal serum biomarkers—FBHCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF—in first-trimester risk assessment for PE. These markers play critical roles in placental development and vascular remodeling and have been previously implicated in adverse pregnancy outcomes, including PE, fetal growth restriction, and stillbirth (King et al. 2022).

The measured levels of the three markers were similar to those measured by other investigators. The levels of AFP, PIGF, β -hCG, and PAPP-A were compared across groups, and AFP levels were significantly increased. Those of PIGF, β -hCG, and PAPP-A were significantly decreased in the PE group compared with the normal group (all $p < 0.05$). The normal group had mean AFP levels of $20.44 \pm 3.66 \mu\text{g/mL}$,

and the PE group had $22.45 \pm 4.11 \mu\text{g/mL}$. PIGF levels were $89.36 \pm 14.99 \text{ U/mL}$ in the normal group and $80.89 \pm 13.70 \text{ U/mL}$ in the PE group. β -hCG was measured as $70.66 \pm 14.23 \text{ ng/mL}$ in the normal group and $63.32 \pm 13.55 \text{ ng/mL}$ in the PE group. PAPP-A levels were $30.28 \pm 5.44 \text{ IU/L}$ in the normal group and $27.08 \pm 4.88 \text{ IU/L}$ in the PE group (Shu and Wang 2025). Studies have consistently shown that women who develop preterm PE have significantly lower PIGF levels in the first trimester than those with normal pregnancies. Furthermore, a significant association is observed between serum PIGF concentrations and the severity of PE, as defined by both gestational age at the time of iatrogenic delivery and neonatal birthweight percentile (Creswell et al. 2023).

The findings demonstrate that low levels of these biomarkers are associated with a higher AR for PE, particularly at 34 and 37 weeks of gestation. Specifically, the screening algorithm identified 2.1%, 9.2%, and 5.5% of the women at increased risk for PE at 34, 37, and 40 weeks, respectively. These data are consistent with prior studies suggesting that combining biochemical markers with maternal characteristics improves the predictive accuracy for PE in early pregnancy (Panaitescu et al. 2018).

Figure 6. Comparison between previous AH and PE risk.

Figure 7. Comparison with family history of PE.

Importantly, normal BMI was significantly associated with lower PE risk at all gestational time points analyzed ($p < 0.001$), and women with normal BMI also exhibited higher mean levels of FBHCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF. This suggests that maternal obesity may affect the placental biomarker profile, contributing to the elevated PE risk observed in this group (Abraham and Romani 2022). While diabetes was associated with a trend toward higher PE risk, statistical significance was not reached, likely due to the small number of diabetic cases. In contrast, prior AH was significantly associated with increased PE risk, particularly at week 40 (AR 1:7, $p < 0.001$), reinforcing its well-established role as a strong clinical risk factor (Weissgerber and Mudd 2015). Interestingly, the biomarker levels themselves—especially PIGF—showed expected trends in their distribution: lower in high-risk patients and higher in those with favorable maternal profiles. This aligns with the pathophysiological understanding that PIGF is decreased in pregnancies complicated by impaired placental perfusion, such as PE (Raghavendra et al. 2025). Overall, the results support the integration of FBHCG, PAPP-A, and PIGF into early screening protocols for PE. The combination of biochemical and clinical risk factors offers a valuable approach for early identification of women at risk, enabling timely surveillance and potential prophylactic interventions such as low-dose aspirin (Ling et al. 2025).

Conclusion

AR for PE was associated with biochemical parameters, BMI, and previous AH, while diabetes showed a non-significant trend toward increased risk ($p > 0.05$). Measurement and further evaluation of these parameters are important for predicting adverse pregnancy outcomes.

However, they should always be interpreted in the context of clinical findings and the mother's overall health status.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This study is financed by the European Union-NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No BG-RRP-2.004-0008.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Abraham T, Romani AMP (2022) The relationship between obesity and pre-eclampsia: Incidental risks and identification of potential biomarkers for pre-eclampsia. *Cells* 11(9): 1548. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11091548>
- Akolekar R, Syngelaki A, Poon L, Wright D, Nicolaides KH (2013) Competing risks model in early screening for pre-eclampsia by biophysical and biochemical markers. *Fetal Diagnosis and Therapy* 33(1): 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000341264>
- Creswell L, O’Gorman N, Palmer KR, da Silva Costa F, Rolnik DL (2023) Perspectives on the use of placental growth factor (PlGF) in the prediction and diagnosis of pre-eclampsia: Recent insights and future steps. *International Journal of Women’s Health* 15: 255–271. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJWH.S368454>
- Fox R, Kitt J, Leeson P, Aye CYL, Lewandowski AJ (2019) Pre-eclampsia: Risk factors, diagnosis, management, and the cardiovascular impact on the offspring. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 8(10): 1625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8101625>
- Karrar SA, Martingano DJ, Hong PL (2024) Pre-eclampsia. *StatPearls*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK570611/>
- King VJ, Bennet L, Stone PR, Clark A, Gunn AJ, Dhillon SK (2022) Fetal growth restriction and stillbirth: Biomarkers for identifying at risk fetuses. *Frontiers in Physiology* 13: 959750. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2022.959750>
- Ling Y, Wu H, Li J, Ma Y, Zhang S, Lu Y, Feng J, Wang S, Liang X (2025) Predictive value of maternal serum placental growth factor, maternal clinical features, and fetal ultrasound indicators in pre-eclampsia. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 25(1): 390. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-025-07517-z>
- National Guideline Alliance [UK] (2019) Hypertension in pregnancy: diagnosis and management. <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng133>
- O’Gorman N, Wright D, Syngelaki A, Akolekar R, Wright A, Poon LC, Nicolaides KH (2016) Competing risks model in screening for pre-eclampsia by maternal factors and biomarkers at 11–13 weeks gestation. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology* 214(1): 103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2015.08.034>
- Panaiteanu A, Ciobanu A, Syngelaki A, Wright D, Nicolaides KH (2018) Screening for pre-eclampsia at 35–37 weeks’ gestation. *Ultrasound in Obstetrics & Gynecology* 52(4): 501–506. <https://doi.org/10.1002/uog.19111>
- Raghavendra R, Bidri S, Yaliwal RG, Patil N, Biradar A, Malapure PS (2025) Placental growth factor as a predictor of adverse maternal outcomes in patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy: A prospective observational study. *Cureus* 17(5): e83285. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.83285>
- Rode L, Wright A, Wright D, Overgaard M, Sperling L, Sandager P, Nørgaard P, Jørgensen FS, Zingenberg H, Riishede I, Tabor A, Ekelund CK, PRESIDE Study Group (2025) Screening for pre-eclampsia using pregnancy-associated plasma protein-A or placental growth factor measurements in blood samples collected at 8–14 weeks’ gestation. *Ultrasound in Obstetrics & Gynecology* 65(5): 567–574. <https://doi.org/10.1002/uog.29204>
- Shu Z, Wang W (2025) Predictive value of prenatal screening markers combined with serum placental growth factor in early pregnancy for pre-eclampsia. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences* 41(2): 598–602. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.41.2.9794>
- Turbeville HR, Sasser JM (2020) Pre-eclampsia beyond pregnancy: long-term consequences for mother and child. *American Journal of Physiology-Renal Physiology* 318(6): 1315–1326. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajprenal.00071.2020>
- Weissgerber TL, Mudd LM (2015) Pre-eclampsia and diabetes. *Current Diabetes Report* 15(3): 9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-015-0579-4>
- Wright D, Syngelaki A, Akolekar R, Poon LC, Nicolaides KH (2015) Competing risks model in screening for pre-eclampsia by maternal characteristics and medical history. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology* 213(1): 62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2015.02.018>